

New Emerging Rare-Earth Doped Luminomagnetic Nanorods for Cellular Imaging Applications

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Abstract

Nanoparticles possessing, both, magnetic and photoluminescence features in a single host lattice have an exceptional utility in multimodal cellular imaging. We have synthesized bifunctional luminomagnetic $Gd_{2-x}Eu_xO_3$ ($x = 0.05$ to 0.5) nanorods, with a diameter of ~ 20 nm and length in ~ 0.6 μm , using hydrothermal method and characterized for its structural, optical and magnetic properties (1). These as synthesized luminomagnetic nanorods exhibit hypersensitive red emission (610 nm) and paramagnetic properties. The cytotoxicity analysis of these nanorods with two human breast cancer cell lines T47D and MDA-MB-231 shows its utility in biomedical applications. Further, the cellular imaging capabilities *in vitro* and *in vivo*, of these luminomagnetic nanorods were also investigated by T47D and MDA-MB-231 cell lines. Moreover, we have also compared the photoluminescence and paramagnetic characteristic of $Gd_2O_3:Eu^{3+}$ nanorods with the spherical nanoparticles of $Gd_2O_3:Eu^{3+}$, to understand the significance of shape of the nanostructure. Hence, these as synthesized luminomagnetic nanorods provides highly biocompatible nanoprobes for cellular imaging applications.

Keywords

Luminescent, Magnetic, bifunctional, cellular imaging, *invitro*, *invivo*

References

Gupta, B. K. *et al.* Bifunctional Luminomagnetic Rare-Earth Nanorods for High- Contrast Bioimaging Nanoprobes. *Sci. Rep.* 6, 32401